

JOURNALISM AS A SCIENCE

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Abstract: For many years of research in the field of journalism, scientists have not been able to develop a single definition of science and achieve an understanding of its subject. Therefore, in this article we analysed this issue.

Key words: countable combination of knowledge, single description of journalism, issue, context, communication, journalism as an institution.

Despite the fact that scientists have been studying journalism for more than a decade, there are still disputes about its subject area. Researchers constantly argue about the place of journalism among the humanities, they do not have unity in understanding its methodology. Like philosophy, journalism does not have an exact scientific definition, which varies both in historical and methodological dimensions, depending on scientific schools and areas of research. According to some researchers, journalism is an independent discipline with its own subject area and special methodology. Another group of scientists considers journalism as part of social disciplines, which does not require the development of a separate methodology. The subject of journalism has been explored in a wide variety of works within the various disciplines of the humanities– sociology, political science, cultural studies, linguistics, etc.

Such a variety of approaches to journalism as a science is due to the lack of a generally accepted definition of the contribution and functions of practical journalism in society. Many traditionally classify journalism as a craft,

and reduce its study to a narrow practical activity. From this point of view, journalism can be viewed as a countable combination of knowledge and skills necessary for the implementation of professional activities. Like approach contributes to the effective training of students and young journalists in the necessary skills. However, this point of view may lead to the inability to adequately assess the impact of journalism on society, to understand the basic principles of journalistic work and the prospects for this activity in a changing world.

Journalism can also be defined as a professional field of activity related to the collection of information, its processing and further distribution through various media channels. The main function of journalism in this case is the modernization of the ideologies of social groups by means of selecting facts, assessments and comments that are timely and important at a specific point in time. Perceived in this way, journalism becomes part of the multifunctional institutions of society - the press, television, radio, the Internet, etc. Another definition of journalism is the actualization of the worldview of social groups by means of selecting facts, assessments and comments that are topical and significant at this time.

The evolution of research in journalism. The process of journalism research is a long and complex process that is still far from over. Moreover, this process develops to a greater extent horizontally, towards the expansion of knowledge. Researchers cover every year more and more new theoretical and practical aspects of journalism. Of course, it cannot be denied that there are comprehensive studies

which form the basis of the whole theory. Although within journalism as a science, a different approach rather prevails: without relying on previous experience, a huge number of different topics and subjects that are not related to each other are being developed.

In fact, scholars became interested in the problems of journalism and its impact on societies immediately after the rapid development of the press in Europe and the United States. For example, Robert Eduard Prutz published his book *The History of German Journalism* in the middle of the 19th century. And already in this work, journalism was defined not just as a practical activity, but as an essential part of society.¹

The first comprehensive studies in journalism appeared in the 1930s.² At this time, such studies were considered as the basis for communication theory. Thus, most of the works were devoted to the influence of the media message on the audience. In addition, at the same time, historical research appeared, which in one way or another affected journalism. Similar works explored the problems of the interaction of various social forces and journalistic activity. It is worth mentioning that these studies were more descriptive than analytical. The works were done on the basis of the individual characteristics of a journalist who was often heroized and presented as an outstanding personality. A typical feature of the researchers of that time was the application of a normative approach to journalism. The researchers described the real state of affairs, and then developed special characteristics and requirements not only for the professional qualities of a journalist, but and to his personality.

At the same time, during this period were published studies that formed the basis for the whole theory journalism. One of the most interesting and influential theories of that time was the concept of "gatekeepers" proposed by D.M. White, who describes a multi-stage approach to information processing.³ This theory and

¹ [1. *Global Journalism Research: Theories, Methods, Findings, Future*, edited by Weaver D. Loffelholz M. — Chichester, Wiley-Blackwell, 2008 — 336-p]

² [2. Rosten L, *The Washington correspondents* - New York: Harcourt, Brace. Reprint of 1937 edition published by Arno Press, 1974 — 250-p]

³ [3. Rosten L, *The Washington correspondents* - New York: Harcourt, Brace. Reprint of 1937 edition published by Arno Press, 1974 — 436-p]

some other studies initiated a wider use of empirical data and their analysis not only on an individual and micro level, but also in the macro environment.

It is difficult to describe all approaches to journalism research in one article. However, we can still identify some of the most important areas of research, which are the subject of a significant number of scientific papers. It seems most logical to start such

description from a sociological approach, which, to one degree or another, is used in most studies in the field of journalism. Within this approach, scholars try to study the social role of journalistic organizations and institutions, identify complex relationships between producers and consumers of media materials, as well as identify specific journalistic structures within the media industry, in society, etc.

Sociological research can become a fundamental scientific basis for the further organization and systematization of research in the field of journalism. The sociological approach allows scholars to study the impact of changes in society on the characteristics of journalistic work. It's hard to deny that the fact that modern structural changes in the economy and society, demographic trends, changes in the management system at macro and micro levels, the evolution of principles political activity leads to fundamental changes in journalism and as institutions that must fulfill public functions and at the same time respond to the needs of the audience. In this case, scientific the basis of sociology may be the only possible structural basis for studying the evolution of journalism institutions.

Despite a long history of journalism, there is neither unified definition for journalism nor a one whole understanding of its subject. Three main subject areas such as texts, contexts and communications should be studied alongside media

economics which has become another key component of media poly system. In the framework of the systematic approach journalism and its subject and tools should

be analyzed as a separate humanitarian science which refers to the human nature and the out world. However there is still a strong requirement to construct the unique system of journalistic research on the basis of existing theories.

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